

Zero Forcing Beamforming With Sidelobe Suppression Using Neural Networks

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Abstract—The use of deep learning in the field of wireless communications has already shown great potential. In this work we present a deep feedforward and a deep recurrent neural network trained as null steering beamformers that target high sidelobes in order to establish low sidelobe level for any desired incoming signal. Using of a zero-forcing algorithm, we apply a sidelobe-damping algorithm where iteratively, a constant number of sidelobes is nullified until a desired sidelobe level is reached. In this way, we can create a dataset which we later use to train our NN models. Using Bayesian optimization, we perform hyperparameter tuning to configure structure and training related parameters for the NNs under examination. The NN models are later fine-tuned using a small dataset containing more demanding cases.

Keywords—adaptive beamforming, hyperparameter optimization, deep neural networks, recurrent neural networks, sidelobe suppression, fine-tuning

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communication systems are being reshaped to meet next-generation networks' escalating demands. These networks require greater data rates, minimal latency, and robust connections. Adaptive Beamforming (ABF), an innovative strategy, is critical for meeting these targets. Traditional beamforming techniques, however, grapple with challenges like sidelobe suppression and slow response times due to their high computational complexity, making them ill-suited for next-generation networks' fast-paced environments. The sidelobe level (SLL), a key parameter in wireless communications, exemplifies one such challenge. High sidelobes can interfere with adjacent channels, negatively impacting system performance and signal clarity. ABF, an advanced signal processing technique, has been crafted to optimise the directional signal transmission or reception in a sensor array by adaptively controlling the array pattern. The goal of ABF is to enhance desired signals and suppress interference, thus effectively managing noise levels. This is achieved by dynamically adjusting the array's radiation pattern in response to the fluctuating signal environment, thereby augmenting system capacity and coverage. This dynamic adjustment is governed by complex weights, or the beamforming vector, applied to each antenna element. The real-time tweaking of these weights ensures the main lobe is directed towards the signal of interest (SOI), minimising interference. Hence, ABF not only improves signal quality but also significantly boosts system capacity and coverage. As 6G networks evolve, the need for efficient ABF has become more

pronounced. Maintaining a low SLL is crucial as high sidelobes can cause significant interference, posing challenges in both signal reception and transmission. Artificial Intelligence (AI), with its learning capability, has emerged as a key solution to tackle these challenges. AI can learn from past scenarios and apply this knowledge to new situations, offering adaptability and efficiency.

This paper presents a novel approach that employs feedforward neural networks (FFNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) to tackle the latency challenges of sidelobe suppression and adaptive beamforming. This novel approach proposes a more efficient and faster method for beamforming by exploiting the capability of neural networks to learn from previous experiences and predict future outcomes. The approach involves a unique iterative method of continuously dampening the high sidelobes of the radiation pattern by adding a constant number of nulls towards their directions using the Null Steering Beamforming (NSB) algorithm. By employing this neural network-based approach, we aim to enhance the speed and accuracy of beamforming, significantly contributing to the performance and efficiency of 6G networks.

II. RELATED WORK

Significant research has been done in the field of beamforming and sidelobe suppression. There have been several approaches towards lowering the SLL of the radiation pattern [1]- [9]. In [1] the authors use particle swarm optimization (PSO) to control the inter-element spacing and excitation amplitude to achieve low SLL and null placement. A linear array implementation [2] demonstrates how by optimizing the amplitude of the beamforming vector weights low SLL can be achieved. However, the proposed method does not consider beam steering. In [3] low SLL pattern is achieved with successive fast Fourier Transforms of the array factor, for planar arrays of a very large number of elements. Other optimal pattern synthesis approaches can be found in literature, mainly applied to linear antenna arrays with the utilization of evolutionary algorithms like the grey-wolf optimizer [4], the differential search algorithm [5] or the chicken swarm optimization algorithm [6]. These works optimize the element positions and feeding current amplitude and phase to achieve low SLL for the broadside direction of linear antenna arrays. Similar approaches to our work can be found in [7] and [8] where an iterative null-placement method was utilized to place nulls towards the directions of the higher

sidelobes. In [7], conventional ABF techniques are employed to place extra nulls towards the highest sidelobe in an iterative manner for a linear array scenario. Specifically, the method proposed nullifying the highest sidelobe per iteration and the results indicate that an adequate SLL around -20dB can be achieved with a variety of ABF techniques. Similarly, in [8] high sidelobes are reduced in a one-by-one fashion until the required SLL is achieved and an application on a 20×20 element, planar array scenario is shown. Despite the incredibly low SLL achieved, this work only considers the broadside direction of the beam. Additionally, the response time of all previous iterative and evolutionary algorithms is a huge concern when it comes to adaptive beamforming, where such beamforming weight calculations should take place in real time. To our knowledge, there has not been a similar NN-based implementation that maps the angle of arrival (AoA) of the desired incoming signal to a beamforming weight vector that achieves low SLL, able to operate in real-time scenarios.

III. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

A. Null Steering Algorithm

To better describe the problem we want to address, we need to specify a few key components of our application. First, we consider a uniform planar array with 64 isotropic radiating elements in an 8×8 configuration placed at a distance of $d=\lambda/2$ from each other (λ being the wavelength of the operating frequency). The radiation of each element can be regulated by controlling the amplitude and phase of the current fed to this element. Therefore, the collective radiation of the entire UPA can be adjusted with the proper manipulation of these 128 complex values (64 real and 64 imaginary parts), which in turn, comprise the beamforming weight vector. The position of each element can be expressed by the coordinates (i, j) ($i=1, \dots, 8$ and $j=1, \dots, 8$) and we consider $I_{i,j}$ to be its feeding current. Thus, the array factor for any given pair of elevation and azimuth angles (θ, φ) can be expressed as follows:

$$AF(\theta, \varphi) = \sum_{i=1}^8 \sum_{j=1}^8 I_{i,j} \exp(j\beta \mathbf{r}_{i,j} \cdot \mathbf{v}(\theta, \varphi)) \quad (1)$$

where $\beta=2\pi/\lambda$ is the propagation phase constant, $\mathbf{r}_{i,j}$ is the position vector of the (i, j) element and \mathbf{v} is the unit vector towards the direction of observation (θ, φ) . Using (1) we are able to extract the radiation pattern of our UPA where we can observe where the main lobe, side lobes and nulls are placed.

Fig. 1 Vector description

As the array operates in the receiving mode, the currents $I_{i,j}$ function as scaling factors for the signals inputted to each element. Hence, it can be interpreted that $I_{i,j} = w_{i,j}^*$ where

$w_{i,j}$ represents a complex weight that signifies the conjugate of the current present at the input port of the element (i, j) . By controlling these weights, we can change the characteristics of the radiation pattern (e.g., the main lobe or nulls) according to our preferences. This can be done with the use of a beamforming algorithm. In this work, we employ a beamforming algorithm that is capable of steering nulls (i.e., points of minimum antenna gain) towards unwanted directions. These “zero-forcing” or “null steering” algorithms are used in cases where multiple interfering signals arrive at the antenna.

We employ the NSB algorithm which requires a set of AoAs, with the first one being the AoA of the SOI and the rest being interferences. The beamforming weight vector produced by NSB makes sure that the main lobe of the radiation pattern is steered towards the direction of the desired user while nulls are accurately placed towards the AoAs of interfering signals. An important observation to be made here is that if only one AoA is given as input, NSB can serve as a strictly beam-steering algorithm. If $N+1$ is the number of incoming signals, and (θ_n, φ_n) are the AoAs of the n -th signal, the theoretical steering vector for each incoming AoA is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta_n, \varphi_n) = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(j\beta \mathbf{r}_{1,1} \cdot \mathbf{v}(\theta_n, \varphi_n)) \\ \exp(j\beta \mathbf{r}_{1,2} \cdot \mathbf{v}(\theta_n, \varphi_n)) \\ \vdots \\ \exp(j\beta \mathbf{r}_{8,8} \cdot \mathbf{v}(\theta_n, \varphi_n)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Using (2), the array factor of (1) can be re-written as:

$$AF(\theta_n, \varphi_n) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta_n, \varphi_n) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{w} = [w_{1,1} \ w_{1,2} \ \dots \ w_{8,8}]^T \quad (4)$$

is the excitation weight vector and superscript H denotes the Hermitian transpose operation. The steering matrix \mathbf{A} contains the steering vectors that correspond to the AoAs of all incoming signals as shown below:

$$\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}(\theta_0, \varphi_0), \mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \varphi_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_N, \varphi_N)], \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the target beamforming weight vector produced by the NSB beamformer is calculated using the array steering matrix:

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{NSB}} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{v}_1, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{v}_1 = [1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^T \quad (7)$$

is a unit vector of size $N+1$.

Having explained how the null-steering algorithm works, we continue to demonstrate how it is employed to lower the sidelobe level.

B. Tracking and nullifying sidelobes

Identifying the sidelobes on a radiation pattern is equivalent to finding the local maxima and excluding the maximum corresponding to the main lobe. If K is the number of sidelobes that can be found using the array factor, then the

directions of the sidelobes (θ_k, φ_k) ($k = 1, \dots, K$) can be identified when both of the following conditions are satisfied:

- $AF(\theta_k, \varphi)$ is a local maximum, $\forall \varphi \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$
- $AF(\theta, \varphi_k)$ is a local maximum, $\forall \theta \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ]$

The SLL is measured by the ratio of the array factor at the peak of the main lobe to the array factor at the peak of the highest sidelobe. Lowering the highest sidelobes by steering nulls towards their directions has proven to be a successful way of decreasing the overall SLL [8], [9]. However, this is not a one-step process as sidelobes of high array gain may appear after the damping of all initial sidelobes. Therefore, the process of lowering the SLL is an iterative process and for this purpose we use an algorithm explained in Algorithm 1. On each iteration, we first identify the higher sidelobes as the ones that reach an array factor higher than a certain threshold. Then we place nulls at their positions, and check if the desired SLL is reached. If not, we continue to identify the new sidelobes that have been formed, add the extra directions the NSB should place nulls at, and check again if the termination criteria are met. It is important to note that the number of sidelobes exceeding this threshold (*keepSL*) for each case of SOI is not constant. Similarly, the number of nulls added on each iteration to the beamforming task can vary.

Algorithm 1: Recursive sidelobe suppression with null steering

Inputs:
SOI: (θ_0, φ_0) ,
High Sidelobe Threshold: *SLkeep*
NSB Function $NSB(\theta, \varphi)$,
Radiation Pattern of UPA $RP(\text{beamforming_weights})$,
Sidelobe identification function $SL(\text{RadiationPattern}, \text{SLkeep})$,
Number of Nulls per iteration: *maxNullsIter*,
Desired Sidelobe Level: *desiredSLL*,
Maximum Iterations: *maxIterations*
Output: Beamforming weight vector, SLL reached

```

1:  $weights_{NSB} \leftarrow NSB(\theta_0, \varphi_0)$ 
2:  $RadiationPattern \leftarrow RP(weights_{NSB})$ 
   # Returns the sidelobes with a descending order of array factor
3:  $sidelobes \leftarrow SL(RadiationPattern, SLkeep)$ 
   # Return the Array Factor of the first sidelobe
4:  $currentSLL \leftarrow sidelobes[0]$ 
5:  $bestSLL\_found \leftarrow currentSLL$ 
   # Iterative process starts here
6:  $iter \leftarrow 0, nulls = [], bestWeights\_found \leftarrow \text{None}$ 
7: while  $currentSLL > desiredSLL$  and  $iter < maxIterations$ :
8:     if the number of sidelobes found is  $> maxNullsIter$ :
           # Keep only the highest sidelobes
            $sidelobes \leftarrow sidelobes[0:max\_nulls]$ 
9:
10:    End if
11:     $nulls \leftarrow \text{extend list by adding } sidelobes$ 
12:     $weights_{NSB} \leftarrow NSB([\theta_0, nulls_\theta], [\varphi_0, nulls_\varphi])$ 
13:     $RadiationPattern \leftarrow RP(weights_{NSB})$ 
14:     $sidelobes \leftarrow SL(RadiationPattern, SLkeep)$ 
           # If no sidelobes are detected, keep decreasing SLkeep
           # by 10dB until a sidelobe is detected
15:    while  $length(sidelobes)$  is equal to 0:
16:         $sidelobes \leftarrow SL(RadiationPattern, SLkeep-10)$ 
17:    End while
18:     $currentSLL \leftarrow sidelobes[0]$ 
19:    if  $currentSLL < bestSLL\_found$ :
20:         $bestSLL\_found \leftarrow currentSLL$ 
21:         $bestWeights\_found \leftarrow weights_{NSB}$ 
22:    End if
23:     $iter \leftarrow iter+1$ 
24: End while
25: Return  $bestWeights\_found, bestSLL\_found$ 

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However, it is possible to control the maximum number of nulls, *maxNullsIter*, that can be added on each iteration. Moreover, by adjusting the maximum number of iterations (*maxIterations*) we can limit the total number of nulls added to the radiation pattern based on the selection of the *maxNullsIter* value.

C. Feedforward and Recurrent Neural Network implementation

Both NN implementations are intuitive and easy to comprehend. For both types of NN examined, the input is the AoA of the SOI and the output is the 128-value weight vector. Given the simplistic nature of the mapping task and the lack of sequential input, the use of RNNs may seem redundant. However, we chose to examine its potential at this application firstly because we have observed great performance for this specific kind of mapping in the past [10] and second, because in some tasks, the architecture of an RNN might provide better results compared to a simple FFNN, due to hidden structures or patterns in the data that the RNN architecture is able to exploit. Furthermore, RNNs can take advantage of any sequential correlation between the inputs as the internal hidden state of RNNs can capture this information. Another reason can be found when considering the employment of RNNs in a real-world scenario. Predicting the beamforming vector for the next time-step SOI will be greatly benefitted by the context of the previous SOI. As the beamformer tries to maintain the main lobe steered towards the direction of the desired user, the SOI's angular deviation between time-steps will be small. Therefore, the context of the past SOI and the correlated beamforming weights can be useful for the next time-step. We do not examine this scenario in this work, but it remains an interesting perspective for future investigation if the current implementation proves to be promising.

Fig. 2 (Top) Multi-layer Feedforward Neural network implementation, (Bottom) Multi-layer LSTM-based Recurrent Neural Network implementation

IV. DATASET PRODUCTION – PROBLEM STATEMENT

Given the mean SLL achieved in [7] by different beamforming techniques when similar conditions were applied, we feel that a value of -20dB is an adequate initial goal to set for the SLL of the final NN beamformer. In order to achieve such a SLL, we need to make sure that the training dataset will be comprised of records of similar or better performance. Before starting to collect records, we need to identify the most promising tuning of the parameters of Algorithm 1. We look for the combination of *maxNullsIter*/*maxIterations* that guarantees the most efficient dataset production with regard to the SLL each record achieves and

the mean time it takes for such a record to be produced. With *desiredSLL* set to -30dB and *SLkeep* set to -35dB, we perform a statistical analysis on 5×10^3 cases of SOI with *maxNullsIter* varying between 1 and 10 nulls per iteration. It is known that the total maximum number of nulls (*totalMaxNulls*) an antenna array of M elements can produce is $M-1$. Therefore, the maximum number of iterations can be configured according to the *maxNullsIter* value so that for each *maxNullsIter* value:

$$\text{maxIterations} = \left\lfloor \frac{\text{totalMaxNulls}}{\text{maxNullsIter}} \right\rfloor \quad (8)$$

However, having tested the algorithm with different parameters, we know that similar performance can be achieved using 63, 21 and 12 nulls in total. To demonstrate this, Figs. 3 and 4 show the mean SLL and the mean time needed to produce a record each combination offers. It is important to note that the initial mean SLL, where the beamformer simply steers the main lobe without any null placement applied, is -11.4dB. All timing measurements were made on an Apple M1 Max chip.

Fig. 3 Mean SLL reached for different parameter configurations

Fig. 4 Mean production time per record for different parameter configurations

Interestingly, Fig. 3 demonstrates that utilizing a larger number of nulls per iteration will not result in a lower SLL. The more “patient” and “careful” the algorithm is at nullifying sidelobes, the higher the SLL suppression it can reach. It is easy to observe that even though lower *maxNullsIter* values reach lower SLL, the mean production time needed per record is forbidding when considering the production of a large enough dataset (hundreds of thousands of records). Meanwhile, the SLL distribution of the records produced in all three scenarios examined (Fig. 5), indicates that for up to 4 max nulls per iteration, the lower quartiles of these distributions are below -20dB. This way, we know

which configuration can produce records below the desired value of -20dB. Considering all previous results, we choose the combination of 4 *maxNullsIter* per iteration and 5 *maxIterations* (case of 21 total nulls at maximum), which has the best trade-off between the mean production time and the SLL values it can reach.

Fig. 5 Distribution of SLL achieved across the records examined between the variations of the total maximum number of nulls allowed

In this work we consider the operational scenario that covers SOIs which arrive from an angular sector of $\theta \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and $\varphi \in [0^\circ, 180^\circ]$ (as shown in Fig. 6). The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of incoming signals is set to 0dB. We also reduce the angular resolution of possible incoming SOIs to 0.2° , and we expect that the NN will be robust for incoming angles of even higher resolution. Having these parameters set, we proceed to produce the training dataset. For each run, we only keep the NSB weights that achieve a SLL of ≤ -20 dB. We collected a total of 1.1×10^5 records out of which 1×10^4 records will be used for evaluation purposes.

Fig. 6 Angular sector of possible incoming angles of arrival of the SOI

V. HYPERPARAMETER TUNING AND TRAINING OF NNS

In this work we use Bayesian optimization (BO) [11] to tune important structure-related parameters of the NNs. Specifically, the number of hidden layers and their corresponding size, the activation function (for the case of FFNN) are the hyperparameters to be tuned. Finally, we perform a grid search to identify the best combination between learning rate, batch size and dropout rate for the training of these models. For training, we employ the Adam optimizer, and we use the root mean square error (RMSE) as a cost function. To perform BO, we utilized the Botorch framework [12] using 10 initial samples and running the optimization for

50 iterations. On each probing, a 3-fold cross validation is applied to further validate the RMSE value reached with the tuning under examination. For each training, the small dataset of 1×10^4 records is used which is further split using 90/10 split for training and validation evaluation.

TABLE I Hyperparameter Optimization Search Space

Hyperparameters		Possible Picks
Bayesian Optimization	Number of Layers	2:5
	Hidden Layer Size	128:16:1024
	Activation Function (<i>only for FFNN</i>)	[ReLU, tanh, sigmoid]
Grid Search	Learning Rate	[0.01, 0.005, 0.001]
	Batch Size	[64, 128, 256, 512]
	Dropout Rate	[0.0, 0.2, 0.4]

TABLE II Bayesian Optimization Tuning per Layer

Model	No. of Layers	Size per Hidden Layer	Act. Fun. per Hidden Layer	Search Time (hrs)	Val. RMSE
LSTM	4	656, 656, 656, 656	-	1.6	0.031
FFNN	4	272, 592, 976, 816	tanh, ReLU, ReLU, tanh	3.9	0.030

TABLE III Grid Search Training Tuning

Model	Learning Rate	Dropout Rate	Batch Size
FFNN	0.001	0.0	64
LSTM-RNN	0.005	0.0	128

Using the hyperparameter settings suggested above, we train both NN types. During training we apply a learning rate scheduler to decrease the learning rate when a plateau on appears on the validation RMSE progression. Training lasted 2.3 hours (1000 epochs) for the FFNN model and 3.6 hours (1000 epochs) for the LSTM-RNN. All trainings took place on an NVIDIA A100-SXM4-40GB GPU. After training all models we tested their performance on the evaluation dataset of 1×10^4 records. We noticed that the FFNN achieves a mean SLL value of -18.7dB while the LSTM-RNN reached a mean SLL value of -18.3dB.

Fig. 7 Flowchart of method used to collect underperforming cases

In order to improve this performance, we applied a fine-tuning method using transfer learning, we investigated the cases where the NNs underperform, and used Algorithm 1 to create a dataset of optimal solutions for these cases. The flowchart of this improvement method can be seen in Fig. 7. In total we collected 2×10^4 records. Next, these records are used to further train the pre-trained models but for a much lower number of epochs (200 epochs, which corresponds to 3.2 and 4.1 minutes of training for FFNN and LSTM-RNN correspondingly) and with a very low learning rate (0.00001). The performance of these fine-tuned models is shown in Section VI.

VI. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

To evaluate the performance of these NNs on the task of SL suppression, we generated a set of 1×10^4 random incoming directions of SOI that the NNs do not have any prior “experience” on. The SLL achieved either with the proposed Algorithm I, with the configuration of 4 *maxNullsIter* per iteration and 5 *maxIterations* or with the fine tuned NN models can be seen in Table IV.

TABLE IV Performance comparison of Algorithm 1 and proposed NN models

Technique	SLL (dB) [mean/ std]	Mean Response Time (sec)
Algorithm 1 w/ NSB	-18.0/ 5.2	1.76
FFNN	-20.7/ 4.5	0.0002
LSTM-RNN	-20.7/ 4.9	0.0004

Array Factor of Algorithm 1, Nulls Used: 8, (SLL:-23.2dB)

Fig. 8 Array factor produced by Algorithm 1 using 8 nulls for SOI at $(\theta, \varphi) = (43.1^\circ, 38.7^\circ)$

Array Factor of FFNN (SLL:-23.4dB)

Fig. 9 Array factor produced by the proposed FFNN for SOI at $(\theta, \varphi) = (43.1^\circ, 38.7^\circ)$

The results demonstrate that the proposed NN models trained using the records produced by Algorithm 1 with the aforementioned settings have an improved performance and a significantly lower response time than the recursive null steering algorithm used. In Figs. 8 and 9 we show an example of a random incoming SOI coming from $\theta=43.1^\circ$ and $\varphi =$

38.7° and how Algorithm 1 and the proposed FFNN beamformer respond to the task of beamforming with a low SLL. Specifically, these colormap representations are used to depict the antenna radiation magnitude towards different directions in the 3D space. It is an easier way to observe the 3D radiation pattern and distinguish the points of interest (i.e., main lobe, side lobes, nulls). As we see in these figures, the the FFNN-produced radiation pattern has fewer “high” sidelobes than the radiation pattern produced using Algorithm 1 with the settings described earlier. In addition, in this scenario the FFNN manages to surpass the Algorithm 1 in performance, having a lower SLL.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work the potential of basic NN structures in the task of adaptive beamforming with low SLL is investigated. To this end, a recursive sidelobe damping algorithm is employed that places a fixed number of nulls per iteration towards the higher sidelobes that appear. Given the proposed algorithm, the most efficient dataset production is investigated. This is achieved by finding the combination of nulls per iteration and maximum number of iterations that guarantees fast production of beamforming vectors with low SLL. Next, Bayesian optimization is employed to identify the most promising tuning of important structure and training related hyperparameters of the NNs. Finally, after collecting a small dataset of cases where the NNs “underperform”, the models are fine-tuned to increase their performance. When evaluated on 1×10^4 unknown incoming SOI scenarios, both models reach a very promising mean SLL with a mean response time more than 8×10^3 times faster than the mean time needed for the proposed recursive algorithm that was used. The results indicate that with appropriate training and tuning, the proposed NN structures can offer very promising beamforming abilities with a response time that meets the demands of future wireless networks.

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